

IMPORTANT ASPECTS OF INFORMATION SECURITY IN SYSTEMS AND NETWORKS

Ibragimov Nodirjon Nusriddinovich

I.f.f.d (PHD)

Associate professor of AT-Service Department of Tuit injection branch

Abdurakhmanov Vahid Abdumuqim Oglu

TATU injection branch AX-12-20 Group student

Amirov Akbarshokh Dilshod son

TATU injection branch AX-11-20 Group student

Shukurova Sitora Zayir qizi

TATU injection branch TT-12-21 Group student

Gulboeva Sabrina the Gofur girl

TATU injection branch TT-11-22 Group student

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Annotation: this article describes such concepts as the concept of information, types of information, threats to information security and their types, the importance of Information Security. Threats to Information Security have been interpreted on modern grounds.

Key words: information, types of information, types of information, types of security, types of information security, types of Information Security.

An informed society is rapidly forming through this computer network. When traveling to the world of information, the concept of state borders is disappearing. The world computer network is radically changing public administration, which means that the state cannot control the mechanism of information dissemination qolmoqda. Ma it is estimated that 70% of the global national output is related to the scale of information stored in Information Systems. Over the next decade, we witnessed the rapid development of Information Technology and its introduction into all aspects of life, especially in different areas of production. In developed countries, most functioning employees are not engaged in the production sector, but to one degree or another, information processing. Today, not every employee, specialist, student can imagine his activities without information technology. They spend their precious time in front of a computer, relying on "smart machines" to store their priceless information created at the expense of hard work, without thinking about their destruction, breakdown, or theft. In order to preserve such valuable information, ensure their safety, it will be necessary to know and masterfully introduce rules, principles, tools, methods. It is important not only to ensure the safety of valuable information, but also to ensure the safety of Information Systems and their infrastructure.

In the speeches and works of the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov and the current president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, spiritual threats, the need to combat it, national security issues in the tasks and information security, the formation of Information Culture among young people, ensuring freedom of access to information, ensuring information security were widely analyzed. These are moral threats to the independence of Uzbekistan and issues of national security in the field of information. Otamurtov's "globalization and national-spiritual Security" 1, Sh.Umarov and F. "Information security" of mulaydinovs, M.Quranov's "national upbringing", M.Lafasov's "religious extremism: history and essence", X.Jumaniyozov, M.Sobirov's "fundamentals of

globalization", I.Karimov and N.Covered in the works of the Turgunov "fundamentals of Information Security".

It should be remembered that even a small message, directed against human spirituality today, which at first glance seems trivial, can take strength from the intensity of globalization in the information world and cause tremendous damage that is not visible to the eye, but cannot be compensated for by anything. Religious extremist groups, unable to see the Independent progress of our Uzbekistan in the last fifteen years alone, did not employ ne-ne forces to sow the seeds of instability, mislead our people of their choice, to distract them, they used any evil means.

The following factors indicate the relevance of this topic:

- to reveal that the ideological threat is a serious threat to the development of society;
- highlighting the features of the manifestation of globalization processes and spiritual and informational threats;
- analysis of the importance of the media in the Prevention of ideological threats;
- lighting that the spiritual threat is a threat to our self and our future;
- analysis of factors for the formation of immunity against spiritual threats;
- with anti-thought thought, anti-idea, anti-ignorance enlightenment explaining the need to fight to young people;
- it consists in the formation of a culture of obtaining information in the fight against various spiritual and informational threats in our society.

Today, the importance of information in the life of any progressive society is constantly increasing. From the distant past, information about the military-strategic importance of the state is strictly kept secret and protected. Currently, information related to production technologies and the sale of products has the appearance of a commodity, and the demand for it in the domestic and foreign market is increasing. Information technology is regularly perfecting in the areas of automation and Information Protection. The progress of modern information technology is observed in combination with such negative phenomena as industrial espionage, computer crime, unauthorized access to confidential information, transformation, loss. Therefore, Information Protection is an important state task in any country. The need for information protection in Uzbekistan is reflected in the creation of a state system of Information Protection and the development of a legal framework for information security. " On informatization"," on the preservation of state secrets"," on the legal protection of programs and databases of electronic computing machines " and other laws and a number of government decisions were adopted and implemented. Not everyone understands how information can be lost and what consequences it will have. For example, hackers Yahoo.com, Amazon.com companies such as and even the Space Research Agency have caused significant damage to NASA. RSA Security, one of the largest imperfections of the security service market, was subjected to a hoax a few days after an impromptu statement about the existence of a measure against any taxidist.

Conclusion

The effective use of this resource ensures the security of the country and the successful formation of a democratically informed society. In such a society, the speed of information exchange rises, the application of advanced information communication technologies in the collection, storage, processing and use of information expands. Information in various ways has entered our daily lives through the internet network of international computers,

regardless of the location of God. An informed society is rapidly forming through this computer network. When traveling to the world of information, the concept of state borders is disappearing. The world computer network is radically changing public administration, which means that the state cannot control the mechanism of information dissemination. Therefore, problems such as illegal access to existing information, their use and loss have become relevant. All this leads to a decrease in the level of information security of the individual, society and the state. The problem of ensuring the information security of the state is a fundamental and integral part of ensuring national security, and Information Protection is one of the primary issues of the state.

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